

**QISHLOQ XO‘JALIGI EKINLARINI HOSILDORLIGINI
MODELLASHTIRISH SAMARADORLIGI**

AGRICULTURAL CROP MODELING EFFICIENCY

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada ekin dinamik modellari yaratilishi, qollanilishi tahlil qilingan va foydalanish sohalari, afzalliklar va kamchiliklari keltirilgan.

Kalit soʻzlar: CropSyst, iqlim oʻzgarishi, DSSAT, APSIM, hosildorlik

Abstract: This article analyzes the development and use of crop dynamic models, and using, advantages, and disadvantages.

Key words: CropSyst, climate change, DSSAT, APSIM, yield

Global isish va uning bilan bogʻliq iqlim oʻzgarishi dunyo mamlakatlarining qishloq xoʻjaligiga sezilarli taʼsir koʻrsatmoqda. Iqlim oʻzgarishi boʻyicha xalqaro qoʻmita (IPCC, 2013) ning maxsus dokladida, 1986-2005 yy. davriga nisbatan, 2016-2035 yy. mobaynida yer yuzasiga yaqin oʻrtacha global havo harorating oʻzgarishi 0,3-0,7 °C oraligʻida boʻlishi qoʻrsatilgan. Shu bilan birgalikda, oʻrtacha global havo haroratining ortishi bilan kunlik va mavsumiy davrlarda ekstremal yuqori temperaturalar tez-tez va ekstremal past temperaturalar kamroq kuzatilishi qayd etilgan. Iqlim oʻzgarishi tasirlarini yumshatish maqsadida qishloq xoʻjaligi ekinlarini modellashtirish orqali kelajakda hosildorlikni bashoratlash mumkin. Bunda ekin dinamik modellarini tanlash va samarali foydalanish yaxshi natijalarni beradi. Dinamik ekin modellari turlicha boʻlib, quyida ularni koʻrib chiqamiz.

Avstraliyada CERES oʻsimlik va tuproq modellari bilan toʻplangan tajribaga asosan APSIM-Nwheat modelining qismlari rivojlantirilgan (Keating et al., 2003). APSIM-Nwheat ekinni simulyatsiyalaydigan model boʻlib, turli qismlardan iborat.

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Shulardan biri tuproq namligi, azot, o‘simlik qoldiqlari, o‘simlik o‘sishi va rivojlanishi hamda ularning o‘zaro ta’siri kabi jihatlarni o‘z ichiga qamrab oladi. Ushbu jihatlarni esa kunlik ob-havo ma’lumotlari to‘g‘ridan-to‘g‘ri boshqaradi. Model potensial hosildorlikni hisoblaydi, bu esa o‘simlikda kasallik va zararkunandalar, poyaning yotib qolishi kuzatilmaganda, dala maydoni esabegona o‘tlardan toza holatda, ammo harorat, quyosh radiatsiyasi, suv va azotozuqasi ta’minoti cheklangan sharoitda erishilgan hosildir (Jones and Kiniry, 1986; Reynolds et al., 2007).

Hozirgi kunda ko‘pchilik modellarda o‘simlikning o‘sishi va rivojlanishini son va jarayon nuqtai nazardan tavsiflashda fiziologiya, agronomiya, agrometeorologiya, tuproqshunoslik kabi turli ixtisosliklar jalb etiladi (James and Cutforth, 1996). Natijada ekinning suvdan foydalanishi e’tiborga olingan holda uning hosildorlik funksiyasini aniqlik bilan ishlab chiqishga imkon yaratildi (Steduto, 1997).

CropSyst modelining turli iqlim va tuproq-ekologik sharoitlarda ekin hosildorligi va boshqa ko‘rsatkichlarni simulyatsiyalash imkoniyatlari adabiyotlarda keng yoritilgan: sug‘orish tartibotlari (Stöckle et al., 1994, 1997, 2003); o‘simliklarning biomassa to‘plashi; barg sathi, o‘simliklar suv va azot o‘zlashtirishi (Pala et al., 1996; Stöckle and Debaeke, 1997); suv va azotmuvozanati (Ventrella and Rinaldi, 1999; Stöckle et al., 2003); almashlab ekish (Stöckle et al., 2003); tuproqqa ishlov berish tizimi (Pannkuk et al., 1998; Stöckle et al., 2003).

Shunday bo‘lishiga qaramay, talab va sharoitni inobatga olgan holda ma’lum maqsadga javob beradigan maqbul modelni tanlash qiyinchilik tug‘diradi. Maqsadga javob beradigan aniq modelni tanlashda uchta mezonga e’tibor qaratiladi (Hansen, 2002): 1) o‘zgaruvchan ko‘rsatkichlarning e’tiborga olinishi va qamrov ko‘lami; 2) aks ettirilgan biofizikaviy jarayonlarning aniqlik darajasi; 3) model va undan foydalanuvchilarni qo‘llab-quvvatlashi. To‘rtinchi omil yuqoridagilarga nisbatan yanada qattiqroq talab qo‘yadi, ya’ni to‘plangan ma’lumotlarning yaroqliligi va sifati. Shular e’tiborga olinsa, maqsad uchun qo‘llash mumkin bo‘lgan modellar soni albatta qisqaradi. Ko‘rsatib o‘tilgan ushbu talablar CropSyst, ya’ni ekin yetishtirish tizimini simulyatsiyalash modelida jamlangan (Stöckle et al., 1994) va bizning tadqiqotlarimiz uchun ma’quldir.

Qishloq xo‘jaligi ekinlari hosildorligi va boshqa ko‘rsatkichlarni modellashtirishda har bir model o‘zining aniqligi va talab qiladigan ma’lumotlar to‘plami bilan farqlanadi. Masalan, yakka ekinning o‘sishi, rivojlanishi va hosilini

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bashoratlashda GOSSYM modeli (Watkins et al., 1998) yoki uning hosilalari bo‘lgan COTONS (Jallas et al., 2000) va Cotton2K (Haim et al., 2008) ni misol tariqasida ko‘rsatish mumkin. Shunga qo‘shimcha ravishda, agronomik jihatdan ekin hosili kabi ko‘rsatkichlarni rejalashtirish va tegishli qarorlar qabul qilishda CropSyst, DSSAT, APSIM, RZWQM, Ecosys va boshqa modellardan keng foydalaniladi (Jones and Kiniry, 1986; Hanson et al., 1999; Keating et al., 2001; Grant et al., 2006).

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro‘yxati

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